

INTERFACIAL EFFECT ON MICROFRACTURE IN FILAMENT UNIT AND FABRIC STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

In order to clarify the interfacial effect on microfracture of glass fiber composites, the initial microfracture was evaluated from two types of coupon; single filament of glass fiber and single ply of glass cloth composites. In both composites, glass fiber was treated with silane coupling agent, anilinopropyltrimethoxysilane, under different treatment conditions. Regardless of the fabric structure, the occurrence of initial microfracture virtually depended on the interfacial function of silane coupling. The fabric structure appeared to depress such an interfacial function.

INTRODUCTION

Our final aim is to estimate the contribution of interfacial reinforcement to composite performance which is necessary for composite design. However, the interfacial reinforcement mechanism is not so clear as to evaluate the interfacial effect. Even if we want to design the interfacial region (interphase), the correlation between the structure and the mechanics in the interphase is too known to depend on experimental art. We then need the evaluation of interfacial properties from both molecular and mechanical viewpoints.

At first, we have analyzed silane on glass fiber for GFRP qualitatively and quantitatively using pyrolysis gas chromatography (pyrolysis GC-FTIR) [1]. This technique gives the value of fixation of silane to glass fiber by rinsing silane-treated glass fiber with an organic solvent to remove the physisorbed silane. The change of fixation with silane concentration in the treatment has showed that industrial silane treatment gives no layer silane structure [2]. Silane molecules on glass fiber seems to form a kind of disordered siloxane sequence structure. Such a structure has been expected to reflect the mechanical properties at the interface [3].

From the mechanical viewpoint, we have adopted the embedded single filament test which seems to be the most useful test to evaluate the interfacial strength. However, the fragmentation method, generally employed for the analysis in embedded single filament test, has been found to have some ambiguous points to get the critical fiber length which is correlated to the shear stress at the interface [4,5]. The most ambiguous definition is to judge if the fragments are no longer broken under sufficient strain of coupon. In another way to avoid this point, we have had an

attention to the first fracture along embedded filament. Eventually, we have proposed '*interfacial transmissibility*' as a mechanical parameter at the interface [3, 6]. This parameter has been derived from the assumption that the first fracture stress is equal to the fiber strength. As described previously [3, 5, 7, 8], the interfacial transmissibility is suitable to many kinds of matrix resin, and is useful to the understanding of the correlation between interfacial structure and mechanical functionality at the interface, compared with critical fiber length in fragmentation method.

The first fracture method is meant to estimate the interfacial effect of the initial microfracture substantially. As a next step, we have developed the technique to measure the initial microfracture in single ply of fabric composite [9, 10]. This technique gives a parameter, '*initial microfracture stress*', and is useful to evaluate the contribution of interfacial effect to the composites with fabric structure. In this presentation, '*interfacial transmissibility*' is compared with '*initial microfracture stress*' under various condition in silane treatment of glass fiber. This comparison is expected to show the interfacial role of silane coupling with fracture process.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and Silane Treatment

Matrix resin used in this study was a bisphenol-A type epoxy resin (Epikote 828), and silane coupling agent was anilinopropyltrimethoxysilane (AnPS). E-glass strand and E-glass cloth were treated with 1.0 w/w/% of AnPS according to the industrial process, 'dip-cure'. The glass fiber was dipped into aqueous 0.2 M acetic acid solution including AnPS with different concentration, and dried under different temperatures and times to form the siloxane networks between silane molecules and glass fiber. After the treatment, the fiber was rinsed with methanol to remove physisorbed silane from glass fiber. The fixation of AnPS was determined according to the previous procedure [1].

Preparation of Coupon and Test Method

For the preparation of embedded single filament coupon, a filament of silane-treated glass strand was subjected to the coupon: The resin was mixed with 11 parts of a hardening catalyst, triethylenetetramine. The mixture was poured into a mold holding a glass filament with tension of 10 g, and was cured at 50 °C for 80 min and at 100 °C for 60 min as a post-cure. The dimension of the mold resulted in a coupon with 1 mm in thickness, 6 mm in width and 15 mm in gage length. The first fracture was measured according to the previous paper [6]. Finally, the interfacial transmissibility was calculated from the values of fiber strength and of apparent fracture strength at the first fracture.

For singly ply composite, the resin with the hardening catalyst was impregnated into the glass cloth, and cured in the same procedure as for single filament coupon under 0.1 kg/cm². The dimension of the coupon resulted in 120 mm in length and 20 mm in width. The initial microfracture stress was determined under the condition that tension was loaded toward the warp yarn direction according to the procedure in the previous paper [9].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Interfacial Transmissibility for single filament

In single filament test, the interfacial transmissibility has been evaluated with different curing times, as shown in Figure 1. The fixation of silane deposit on glass fiber has also been obtained. In this treatment, silane deposit on glass fiber has the same thickness and only the fixation increases

Figure 1. Interfacial transmissibility using silane-treated (○) and silane-treated/MeOH washed (●) fibers and fixation (---) as a function of curing time at 110 °C.

with curing time. The resulting interfacial transmissibility gives a peak regardless of rinsing with methanol. Such a change is related to the silane fixation [8]: A small quantity of fixed silane at the initial curing time little produces interfacial reinforcement, while much higher fixation gives the mature silane network that prevents the penetration of resin into silane interphase. Eventually, the developing network of silane deposit seems to give a maximum number of effective reaction sites to resin molecules. In other words, silane networks structure is a dominant factor in penetration of resin molecules into silane network in the following order; immature, mature, and developing silane networks. The removal of physisorbed silane with methanol enhances the chemical bonding, because this promotes the penetration of resin molecules into silane network and makes some buried reaction sites active to resin.

Initial Microfracture in Single Ply Cloth Composite

In single ply test, the initial microfracture stress has been evaluated at the same condition as in single filament test, as shown in Figure 2. The silane fixation has also been obtained with

Figure 2. Initial microfracture stress of silane-treated glass cloth (○) and silane-treated / MeOH-washed glass cloth (●) as a function of curing time at 110 °C

different curing times. The change of fixation with curing time is similar to that in single filament test. This means that silane is fixed by the same mechanism in spite of fabric structure. In industrial silane treatment process, curing condition is a major factor to the fixation. During the cure process, silanes competitively react to the silanol of glass fiber and to other silane molecules on glass fiber and form silane network with siloxane sequence [2]. Eventually, the network structure in single ply test is the same as in single filament test.

In single ply test, the change of initial microfracture stress with fixation is similar to that of interfacial transmissibility in single filament test. In particular, the interphase consisting of only the fixed silane gives a maximum of initial microfracture stress as well as that in single filament test. Such a resemblance to single filament test means that the interfacial function of silane appears initial microfracture regardless of fabric structure. In addition, it should be noted that the initial microfracture is possible to be a parameter for interfacial reinforcement.

Fabric Effect on Microfracture

Figure 3 shows the change of interfacial transmissibility and fixation with silane concentration. The fixation of silane gives a maximum in silane concentration. The significant drop in the fixation occurs at extremely lower concentration. This drop is often appeared in industrial silane treatment. As shown in Figure 4, glass cloth also gives the same behavior. This is due to a little of silanol group of glass fiber and a low reaction between dilute silanes on glass fiber [2].

As shown in Fig. 3, the interfacial transmissibility also gives a maximum near 70 % of fixation. In particular, the removal of physisorbed silane elevates the interfacial transmissibility extremely. This result suggests that the interfacial effect on mechanical property at the interface is similar to that as shown in Figures 1 and 2. In other words, the removal of physisorbed silane appears different effects; the lowering of surface wettability to resin, the enhancement of chemical bonding to resin, and the encourage of deformable silane layer in order of silane concentration. In single ply test, the change of initial microfracture stress and fixation with silane concentration is similar to that in single filament test, as shown in Figures 4 and 5. However, the magnitude of interfacial effect is significantly changed by the tensile direction from warp to weft, as shown in Fig. 5. This result shows that the interfacial effect is depressed by a little change of fabric structure such as the heterogeneous structure of glass fabric in direction and the distribution of the local volume fraction of resin in composites, as described in the previous paper [10].

Figure 3. Change of interfacial transmissibility with silane concentration; treated under 90 °C for 20 min.

Figure 4. Change of fixation of silane on glass cloth with concentration of silane solution.

Figure 5. Change of initial microfracture stress with silane concentration under tension toward warp (○) and weft (●) directions; silane curing condition.

Interfacial Function and Microfracture

The initial microfracture technique, as shown in first fracture method and single ply test, is found to be easily correlated with the structure and function of silane coupling. However, the fracture of composite coupon depends on many factors such as fabric structure, volume fraction, and the mechanical property of matrix resin. Indeed, it has been unreasonable to correlate the fracture strength of coupon with silane coupling function, as described in the previous paper [10]. Such a situation suggests that interfacial reinforcement by silane coupling function mainly reflects faultless interface before the occurrence of microfracture. If the failure or yield at the interface occurs, silane coupling function is disappeared or ineffective, compared with other failure factors; the significant change of stress distribution by microfracture, the fracture toughness in crack development from microfracture, and so on. Therefore, in order to evaluate the interfacial function to reinforcement, it is important to observe and evaluate the microfracture in the composite.

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